

Nucleation studies in supersaturated aqueous solutions of chromate doped potassium dihydrogen phosphate

C. Mahadevan^{a*} and C. S. Jegatheesan^b

Department of Physics, ^aS. T. Hindu College, Nagercoil-629 002, India

^bSivanthi Aditanar College, Nagercoil-629 501, India

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Induction periods have been measured for various supersaturated aqueous solutions of potassium dihydrogen phosphate doped with potassium chromate by the direct vision method. Various critical nucleation parameters have been calculated based on classical theory for homogeneous nucleation. The critical nucleation parameters increase with the increase in concentration of chromate doping in the KH_2PO_4 solutions.

The induction period (τ) can be measured^{1,2} and used to calculate certain critical nucleation parameters, like interfacial tension (σ) of the solid relative to its solution, energy of formation (ΔG) of a critical nucleus, the radius of the nucleus (r) in equilibrium with its solution, etc. based on the classical theory for homogeneous nucleation.

We report here the results of nucleation studies on supersaturated aqueous solutions of KDP doped (impurity concentration in the range 2000–10000 ppm) with K_2CrO_4 (dopant added in the aqueous solution of KDP) in six different but definite KDP : K_2CrO_4 molecular ratios, viz. 1 : 0.0 (pure KDP), 1 : 0.002, 1 : 0.004, 1 : 0.006, 1 : 0.008 and 1 : 0.010.

Results and Discussion

The measured induction periods are presented in Table 1. The value of τ decreases and hence the nucleation rate increases as the supersaturation and concentration of doping of the aqueous solution increase. Values of ΔG and r decrease when the supersaturation increases. This result is similar to that observed by previous workers for their systems²⁻⁷.

Deviation from linearity at lower supersaturation levels has been observed in the plots of $\ln \tau$ vs $1/\ln^2(S)$ (plots not shown) where S is the supersaturation. Previous authors also have observed a similar result with their systems²⁻⁷. This was explained by considering the heterogeneous nucleation caused by the unwanted impurity particles present in the solvent^{6,7}. The linearity is expected to observe at higher supersaturations as the effect of the unwanted impurity particles present in the solvent is dominated over by the presence of more amount of solute. However, the maximum practical limit for the induction period measurement does not allow the supersaturation to exceed 1.8 (if exceeds nucleation occurs before the attainment of supersaturation). Hence, in order to reduce the effect of these practical difficulties on the nucleation

parameters, the results were obtained in the present study using the slopes determined in the linear region of the plots of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(S)$.

It can be seen from Table 1 that the nucleation parameters (σ , ΔG and r) increase with the increase in concentration of K_2CrO_4 doping in the KDP solution. Similar results were observed⁵ for the dopants (having the same doping ratios as in the present study) KBr and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. However, in the case of KCl and KNO_3 dopants⁴, the nucleation parameters decrease with increase in concentration of doping in the KDP solution. A qualitative explanation can be attempted by considering the densities of the dopants. The densities¹ of KCl, KNO_3 , KH_2PO_4 , $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, K_2CrO_4 , and KBr are respectively 1.98, 2.11, 2.30, 2.68, 2.73 and 2.75 g cm^{-3} . The nucleation parameters increase with doping concentration for the denser dopants ($\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, K_2CrO_4 and KBr) and decrease with the doping concentration for the rarer dopants (KCl and KNO_3).

Table 1. Induction periods and nucleation parameters

System (KDP : K_2CrO_4)	S	τ s	σ mJm^{-2}	ΔG kJmol^{-1}	r nm
Pure KDP	1.4	720	7.278	18 144	0.994
	1.5	630		12 488	0.825
	1.6	510		9 297	0.712
	1.7	395		7 296	0.630
	1.8	270		5 942	0.569
1 : 0.002	1.4	495	7.575	20 451	1.035
	1.5	465		14 076	0.858
	1.6	415		10 479	0.741
	1.7	325		8 223	0.656
	1.8	225		6 697	0.592
1 : 0.004	1.4	370	7.678	21 302	1.049
	1.5	325		14 662	0.870
	1.6	280		10 915	0.751
	1.7	230		8 566	0.665
	1.8	155		6 976	0.600

Table-1 (contd.)

1 : 0.006	1.4	270	7.718	21.638	1.054
	1.5	250		14.894	0.875
	1.6	215		11.087	0.755
	1.7	160		8.701	0.669
	1.8	110		7.086	0.603
1 : 0.008	1.4	195	8.437	27.238	1.152
	1.5	170		18.748	0.956
	1.6	140		13.957	0.825
	1.7	105		10.952	0.731
	1.8	65		8.920	0.659
1 : 0.010	1.4	155	9.760	43.740	1.333
	1.5	135		30.111	1.106
	1.6	105		22.416	0.954
	1.7	65		17.590	0.845
	1.8	25		14.327	0.763

Experimental

KH_2PO_4 and K_2CrO_4 (AnalaR) and double-distilled water were used. Aqueous solutions of various supersaturated concentrations were prepared by dissolving the required amount of KDP and K_2CrO_4 at temperatures slightly higher than the saturation temperature. Supersaturation was obtained by natural cooling.

Induction periods (τ) were measured by following the reported procedures⁷. Experiments were performed at five selected degrees of supersaturation, viz. 1.4, 1.5, 1.6, 1.7 and 1.8 at 32°. The volume of solutions taken in the nucleation cells was maintained at 25 ml in all the experiments. Several nucleation runs were carried out under controlled and unstirred conditions. Reproducible results within an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$ were obtained.

Various critical nucleation parameters were calculated following the reported procedures⁷.

K_2CrO_4 doped KDP single crystals grown in the nucleation cell were found to exhibit the scalenohedral (twelve sided) morphology as in the case of pure KDP crystals. Also, the doped crystals were found to have coloured (lemon yellowish due to the effect of the dopant K_2CrO_4 as the colour of the dopant is lemon yellow). The intensity of colour increased with increase in doping concentration of the solution used.

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